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Tumor Circulome in the Liquid Biopsies for Cancer Diagnosis and Prognosis

Alireza Heidari^{1,2,3,4*}, Elena Locci^{1,2,3} and Silvia Raymond^{1,2,3}

¹Faculty of Chemistry, California South University, 14731 Comet St. Irvine, CA 92604, USA

²BioSpectroscopy Core Research Laboratory, California South University, 14731 Comet St. Irvine, CA 92604, USA

³Cancer Research Institute (CRI), California South University, 14731 Comet St. Irvine, CA 92604, USA

⁴American International Standards Institute, Irvine, CA 3800, USA

***Corresponding Author:** Alireza Heidari, Faculty of Chemistry, California South University, 14731 Comet St. Irvine, CA 92604, USA, Email: Scholar.Researcher.Scientist@gmail.com; Alireza.Heidari@calsu.us; Central@aisi-usa.org

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Abstract

New research shows that blood and urine tests can lead to faster and less invasive methods for diagnosing and monitoring different types of tumors. Two studies by the California South University (CSU) Cancer Research Institute (CRI) describe the potential of fluid biopsy to identify and track tumor growth in two very different cancers: bladder cancer and peripheral nerve tumors. Despite the differences between these cancers and their related biopsies, studies show the potential benefits of this relatively new tool in the fight against cancer.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues; Tumors; Prevention; Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

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Introduction

One study reports the development of a urinary biopsy to monitor bladder cancer. By easily collecting urine samples, doctors can determine if the initial treatment has eliminated the cancer or left the remnants of the disease behind. This knowledge can lead to fewer patients undergoing unnecessary surgery. The second study describes a blood biopsy to detect a tumor of the sheath or inner

lining that covers the peripheral nerves. This rare cancer is caused by an inherited genetic disorder called neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1). In patients with NF1, it is difficult to determine whether benign or malignant tumors have formed in the nerve sheath. Our studies show ways to improve cancer management with fluid biopsies that demonstrate accurate diagnosis and monitoring of tumors at different stages of the disease. In the case of bladder cancer, if a urine biopsy detects whether the initial chemotherapy has completely destroyed the tumor, it can help

some patients avoid major surgery to remove the bladder, and for NF1, if we can between cancerous tumors. And to differentiate pre-cancerous, we pave the way for early detection of cancer in inherited conditions that predispose people to cancer [1-490].

Results and Discussion

Patients with bladder cancer who have invaded the underlying muscle usually undergo chemotherapy to shrink the tumor, followed by surgery to remove the bladder. Bladder resection, which can include prostate and seminal vesicle removal for men and removal of the uterus, ovaries, and part of the vagina for women, reduces the risk of cancer recurrence. But some patients may respond well to initial chemotherapy and do not need to have their bladder or adjacent organs removed. Unfortunately, today there is no way to diagnose which patients may not need bladder resection, a method that has a major impact on quality of life. Urine biopsy performed by Alireza Heidari *et al.* [1-490]. May in the future be a way to determine which patients may safely avoid bladder resection. In this study, researchers analyzed DNA in the urine of healthy people and patients with bladder cancer undergoing chemotherapy. After chemotherapy, but before surgery to remove the bladder, the scientists were able to identify the remaining DNA in the urine of cancer patients that would not otherwise be detected. All patients underwent surgery to remove the bladder. The researchers found tumor DNA in the urine of patients whose bladders later showed remnants of the tumor, even after chemotherapy. In contrast to those patients who responded well to so-called chemotherapy, there was no evidence that tumors remained in the bladder after surgical removal; they also did not show any tumor DNA in their urine before surgery. While the test is not yet sensitive enough to guide treatment decisions, Chadori said the study paves the way for further improvements to identify patients who can maintain their

bladder after chemotherapy. Patients with NF1 are prone to cancer, and peripheral nerve sheath tumors are the most common cause of death for such patients. These cancers usually originate from benign tumors, and it is often difficult to distinguish between benign and malignant types of these tumors. In the future, fluid biopsy may help physicians determine when malignant tumors are malignant in patients with NF1, and improve early cancer diagnosis and early treatment in patients at high risk for cancer.

Conclusion

There are signs of gastritis or inflammation of the bladder that may also indicate bladder cancer. If additional signs and symptoms such as weight loss, vomiting and pain appear not only in the abdomen and defecation, you need to take the necessary measures, including gastroscopy. An MRI should also be done when vomiting. Chronic inflammation, especially gastritis, can lead to cancer; therefore, all persons 35 years of age and older are required to undergo gastroscopy once a year.

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Authors' Brief Biographies

Prof. Dr. Alireza Heidari, Ph.D., D.Sc. is a Full Distinguished Professor and Academic Tenure of Chemistry and also Enrico Fermi Distinguished Chair in Molecular Spectroscopy at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. He has got his Ph.D. and D.Sc. degrees from California South

University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. Furthermore, he has double postdocs in Project Management, Oncology, Human Cancer Tissues and Synchrotron Radiation from Monash University, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia and also in Nanochemistry and Modern Molecular Electronic–Structure Computations Theory from California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA. His research interests include Biophysical Chemistry, Biomolecular Spectroscopy, Quantum Chemistry, Nanochemistry, Modern Electronic Structure Computations, Theoretical Chemistry, Mathematical Chemistry, Computational Chemistry, Vibrational Spectroscopy, Molecular Modelling, Ab initio & Density Functional Methods, Molecular Structure, Biochemistry, Molecular Simulation, Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Medicinal Chemistry, Oncology, Synchrotron Radiation, Synchrocyclotron Radiation, LASER, Anti–Cancer Nano Drugs, Nano Drugs Delivery, ATR–FTIR Spectroscopy, Raman Spectroscopy, Intelligent Molecules, Molecular Dynamics, Biosensors, Biomarkers, Molecular Diagnostics, Numerical Chemistry, Nucleic Acids, DNA/RNA Monitoring, DNA/RNA Hypermethylation & Hypomethylation, Human Cancer Tissues, Human Cancer Cells, Tumors, Cancer Tissues, Cancer Cells, etc. He has participated at more than five hundred reputed international conferences, seminars, congresses, symposiums and forums around the world as yet. Also, he possesses many published articles in Science Citation Index (SCI)/International Scientific Indexing (ISI), Medline/PubMed and Scopus Journals. It should be noted that he has visited many universities or scientific and academic research institutes in different countries such as United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Scotland, Ireland, Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark, Luxembourg, Romania, Greece, Russia, Estonia, Ukraine, Turkey, France, Swiss, Germany, Sweden, Norway, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, South Africa, Egypt, Brazil, Spain, Portugal, Mexico,

Japan, Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Philippines, South Korea, China, India, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, etc. as research fellow, sabbatical and volunteer researcher or visitor and so on heretofore. He has a history of several years of teaching for college students and various disciplines and trends in different universities. Moreover, he has been a senior advisor in various industry and factories. He is expert in many computer programs and programming languages. Hitherto, he has authored more than twenty books and book chapters in different fields of Chemistry. Syne, he has been awarded more than one thousand reputed international awards, prizes, scholarships and honors. Heretofore, he has multiple editorial duties in many reputed international and peer–reviewed journals, books and publishers. Hitherto, he is a member of more than five hundred reputed international academic–scientific–research institutes around the world. It should be noted that he is currently the President of the American International Standards Institute (AISI), Irvine, California, USA and also Head of Cancer Research Institute (CRI) and Director of the BioSpectroscopy Core Research Laboratory at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA.

Elena Locci is a Ph.D. Candidate under the Supervision of Professor Alireza Heidari at Cancer Research Institute (CRI) and BioSpectroscopy Core Research Laboratory at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA.

Dr. Silvia Raymond, Ph.D., D.Sc. is the current Junior Postdoctoral Research Fellows under the Supervision of Professor Alireza Heidari at Cancer Research Institute (CRI) and BioSpectroscopy Core Research Laboratory at California South University (CSU), Irvine, California, USA.